

Studies on the Continuous Phase in the Vicinity of Emulsion Droplets—Part I

R. PRATAP SINGH AND S. SAHRAN SINGH*

Department of Chemistry, Bhagalpur College of Engineering, Bhagalpur-3

(Manuscript received 4 May 1972; revised 27 August 1972; accepted 10 November 1972)

Different benzene in water emulsions with Naloleate as emulsifying agent were prepared under identical conditions and their creaming characteristics and related physical properties were investigated. The creaming data were fitted in an exponential equation and the characteristic constant λ was determined for each emulsion studied. The λ values were plotted against the corresponding phase-volume ratio ϕ . The $\lambda-\phi$ curve showed a sharp change in slope at a critical ϕ value which led to the assumption of co-spheres of continuous medium enclosing each emulsified droplet. The critical ϕ value obtained from $\lambda-\phi$ curve was utilised in evaluating the ratio of the co-sphere radius to the radius of the emulsified droplet. This ratio was also evaluated from the viscosity data for the system studied by the authors as well as for the systems studied by earlier workers.

THE earlier studies on the nature of the continuous phase in the vicinity of dispersed particles were mainly concerned with the concept of electrical double layers as introduced by Helmholtz¹ and later on extended by Gouy² and Stern³. This led to a possible existence of a parameter⁴ such that its reciprocal represented the distance from the particle. Henry⁵ and also Booth⁶ utilised this parameter in developing equations for correlating data on electrophoretic mobility. As defined, the reciprocal of this parameter is equivalent to the effective diameter of the dispersed particles and leads to the assumption of an apparent increase in the total volume of the dispersed phase.

While investigating Smoluchowski's equation⁷, which takes care of the electroviscous effect in calculating the viscosity of disperse systems, van der Waarden⁸ concluded that the emulsion droplets behaved as if their apparent volumes were larger than their real volumes. According to him the disperse phase droplets are surrounded by a rigid layer of 30-35 Å irrespective of the actual droplet size.

According to Kremnev and Soskin⁹ the microscopically determined interfacial film thickness δ of the dispersed droplets may be regarded as a measure of the hydrated layer surrounding these droplets. It is interesting to note that the existence of a similar hydrated layer was also proposed to explain the volume factor in Sibree's equation¹⁰ for emulsion viscosities. In all the emulsions studied, δ was of the value of nearly 0.01 μ . However, on standing, a limiting emulsion changed spontaneously in the direction of increased film thickness and decreased interfacial area. Kremnev and Soskin¹¹ further concluded that the interfacial area and hence δ were independent of emulsifier concentrations higher than

5%. Also, if it was assumed that the droplets were in virtual contact with each other in a concentrated emulsion, the distance between the adjacent droplets might be taken as 2δ . Another study of Kremnev and Kuibina¹² on Benzene/Water emulsions, having 0.23 to 0.31M Triethanolamine oleate as emulsifier, showed that the film thickness δ was found to be 100 Å. While studying the rate of rise of emulsion droplets under microscope, Fihurovskii and Futran¹³ found that the rate of rise in the absence of any emulsifier was predicted by Stoke's law, but in the presence of an emulsifier the droplet radius r was to be replaced by an effective radius, $\rho = r + \Delta r$. For droplets ranging in diameter from 2 to 20 μ and 0.1% Na-oleate as emulsifier the calculated value of Δr was found equal to 0.25 to 0.30 μ and for 0.82% Na-oleate, Δr equalled 0.5 to 0.55 μ . In an interesting study Bromberg¹⁴ found that the highly concentrated emulsions protected by condensed interfacial films of Na-oleate swelled in water until the mean thickness of the water interstices 2δ was about 4 μ . Centrifuging had the effect of decreasing this to about 1 μ . If water was frozen out, separation of benzene occurred when 2δ was about 0.9 μ .

From the works as cited above, the existence of a layer of considerable thickness surrounding the dispersed droplets in emulsion systems is most obvious. However, a clear understanding about the estimate of the nature of continuous medium as a whole in the vicinity of dispersed droplets needs further investigation. In view of this it was considered of interest to examine the creaming characteristics and related physical properties of some selected emulsion systems in the hope to unravel characteristic system parameters.

Experimental

Materials: Benzene as disperse phase and Na-oleate as emulsifier were B.D.H. (India) and B.D.H.

* Department of Chemistry, Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur-7.

(England) products respectively; while the continuous phase in each case was double distilled conductivity water.

Preparation of emulsion: Different Benzene in water emulsions with Na-oleate as emulsifying agent were prepared following the agent in water method¹⁵. The concentration of the emulsifying agent, temperature, mode and time of stirring were kept constant in each case. The equipment used for stirring was always a mechanical stirrer with four blades having a combined area of 8.6 sq. cm.

Procedure: Emulsions prepared as above were allowed to cream up in graduated glass jars kept in water bath maintained at a temperature of $30^{\circ} \pm 0.2^{\circ}$. The total height of the upper layer of emulsion and the radius of the glass jar were noted in each case. The height of the separating cream from the bottom was noted at various intervals of time. The level of separation, which was not very clear in initial stages, became quite distinct with the lapse of time. The emulsion viscosities were determined using Ostwald viscometer¹⁶, while the specific gravity was measured by standard method using Pyknometer¹⁷.

Results and Discussion

The heights of separating cream L in cms were plotted against corresponding time t in seconds for emulsions of different phase-volume ratios ϕ defined as the ratio of the volume of disperse phase to the total volume of the emulsion. The curves are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Plot of L against t for benzene/water emulsions of different phase-volume ratio stabilised by 1% Na-oleate.

A close observation of the curves in Fig. 1 reveals that the curves with $\phi < 0.4$, representing comparatively dilute emulsions, show an abrupt change in the slope after an initial portion approximating to a straight line; whereas the curves with $\phi > 0.45$ show a gradual change in the slope. However, both the set of curves become exponential in the end. This indicates the existence of a critical value of phase-volume ratio ϕ_c such that $0.4 < \phi_c < 0.45$.

This shows that the creaming process for comparatively dilute emulsions with $\phi < \phi_c$ is different than the creaming process for concentrated emulsions with $\phi > \phi_c$. In view of this, the creaming of dilute emulsions occurring in finite jars or tubes, as in the present study, appears to indicate that the individual emulsion droplets with adsorbed film of emulsifier may be considered to behave as a sphere of infinite viscosity for all practical purposes and follow the Stoke's law till they are undisturbed by the influence of other droplets in their vicinity. As the creaming progresses, the droplets get closer and a situation arises when the interaction among them becomes important. Consequently, a second stage of creaming begins in which the velocity is noticeably less than that predicted by the Stoke's law. With the passage of time this velocity approaches zero signifying the beginning of a third stage of complete separation of the cream. In the case of concentrated emulsions the droplets may be close enough in the beginning for interactions to be prominent and in that case the initial stage in which Stoke's law is applicable may not occur at all. As such the creaming of concentrated emulsions may be represented by the remaining two stages only.

From the above discussions it becomes amply clear that the creaming data, as represented in Fig. 1, may be fitted in the following equation

$$L = L'e^{-\lambda t} \tag{1}$$

where L is the height of the separating cream, measured from the bottom of the jar in which the creaming occurs, t is the time and L' and λ are the constants. L' has the dimension of length and equals L when $t = \infty$; while λ has the dimension of time and equals t for which $\ln L'/L$ is unity. As required by equation (1), the plot of $\text{Log } L$ against $1/t$ should be linear with slope equal to $-\lambda/2.303$ (Fig. 2). Since the emulsions with $\phi < \phi_c$ follow a different creaming

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log L$ against $1/t$ for benzene/water emulsions of different phase-volume ratio stabilised by 1% Na-oleate.

pattern than those with $\phi > \phi_c$, it is expected that the plot of λ against ϕ would show an abrupt change in slope at $\phi = \phi_c$. Accordingly the values of λ were plotted against ϕ in Fig. 3 and it was found that the abrupt change in the slope does occur. The point where the initial and the final linear portions of the plot in Fig. 3 intersect each other gives the value of ϕ_c equal to 0.43.

Fig. 3. Plot of λ against ϕ for benzene/water emulsions stabilised by 1% Na-oleate.

The value of ϕ_c , as defined and determined above, corresponds that volume of disperse phase which after emulsification, under the experimental conditions of the present study, gives a critical emulsion possessing droplets whose average inter droplet distance σ_c is such that the interactions between adjacent droplets start becoming prominent enough to produce abrupt change in slope of λ - ϕ curve (Fig. 3). In this connection it may not be out of place to mention that the coalescence of emulsion droplets expected to contribute towards the change of slope in λ - ϕ curve is hardly appreciable in comparatively stable emulsions and may safely be neglected. Of course, the situation will change if the separation of cream is complete and the initial repulsion between the electrical double layers of adjacent emulsion droplets is overcome by van der Waal type attraction at distances of their approach much shorter than σ_c .

Thus it is reasonable to assume a co-sphere of each emulsified droplet specifying the spherical portion of the continuous medium which encloses the droplet; the radius being such that the co-spheres touch each other when the corresponding adjacent droplets are σ_c apart in an emulsion with $\phi = \phi_c$. It follows that the co-spheres of adjacent droplets with inter droplet distance greater than σ_c , belonging to emulsions with $\phi < \phi_c$, do not touch each other and consequently there is no droplet interaction; whereas co-spheres of adjacent droplets with inter droplet distance shorter than σ_c , and belonging to emulsions with $\phi > \phi_c$, overlap each other giving rise to significant droplet interaction.

If we make a further simplification by assuming an average drop diameter for the emulsions under study, it may be possible to calculate the ratio of the emulsion droplet radius to the radius of the corresponding co-sphere. Thus comparing the volume v of disperse phase consisting of n droplets with

average radius r_d and the total volume v_s of corresponding co-spheres with average radius r_s , we have

$$r_s/r_d = (v_s/v)^{1/3} \quad (2)$$

If we consider a special case in which $\phi = \phi_c$ with adjacent co-spheres touching and also satisfying the condition of close packing of spheres¹⁸ then

$$v_s = 0.74V \quad (3)$$

and

$$v = \phi_c V \quad (4)$$

where V is the total volume of the emulsion. With these values of v_s and v , equation (2) gives

$$r_s/r_d = (0.74/\phi_c)^{1/3} \quad (5)$$

In order to calculate the numerical value of the ratio r_s/r_d , for the emulsion under study, the numerical value of ϕ_c is determined from Fig. 3.

Fig. 4. Plot of viscosity against corresponding phase-volume ratio for benzene/water emulsions stabilised by 1% Na-oleate.

The validity of equation (5) is tested if the ϕ_c obtained from considerations of any other emulsion property, which is affected by the interaction of the co-spheres of emulsion droplets, gives the same ratio r_s/r_d . For this, emulsion viscosities η were plotted against corresponding values of ϕ in Fig. 4 and as required the value of ϕ_c was found again equal to that determined from λ - ϕ curve (Fig. 3). It was interesting to plot the viscosities again corresponding ϕ values of the systems studied by Neogy and Ghosh¹⁹ and by Jain and Sharma²⁰. In each plot there was a critical value of ϕ_c beyond which a sharp change in the viscosities occurred enabling the evaluation of corresponding ratio r_s/r_d from equation (5). The values of ϕ_c for the system under investigation as calculated from Figs. 3 and 4 and for other systems as calculated from η - ϕ plots are given in Table I which also includes the values of r_s/r_d for each system as calculated from equation (5).

It is believed that the assumption of co-spheres leading to a fixed ratio of its radius to the radius of the corresponding emulsion droplet may lead to further insight in explaining a host of experimental data on emulsion systems.

TABLE I. VALUES OF ϕ_c AND r_0/r_d FOR DIFFERENT EMULSION SYSTEMS

Sl. No.	Emulsion system	Emulsifying agent	ϕ_c	r_0/r_d
1.	Benzene/Water	Na-oleate	0.430	1.198
2.	Water/Benzene*	Mg-oleate	0.400	1.227
3.	Xylene/Water*	Cetyl Dimethyl Benzyl Ammonium Chloride.	0.460	1.170
4.	Xylene/Water*	Cetyl Pyridinium Bromide.	0.460	1.170
5.	Xylene/Water*	Cetyl Trimethyl Ammonium Bromide.	0.450	1.180
6.	K-oil/Water†	Manoxol O T	0.290	1.367
7.	K-oil/Water†	Cetyl Pyridinium Bromide.	0.320	1.322
8.	K-oil/Water†	Tween-60	0.330	1.308

* Values of η and ϕ were taken from the data of Neogy and Ghosh¹⁹.

† Values of η and ϕ were taken from the data of Jain and Sharma²⁰.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express their grateful thanks to Professor A. B. Lal, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur-7 for providing laboratory facilities and his interest in the

work. One of us (S.S.S.) thankfully acknowledges U.G.C. for providing contingency grant.

References

1. H. HELMHOLTZ, *Wied. Ann.*, 1879, **7**, 537.
2. G. GOUY, *Compt. rend.*, 1909, **149**, 654; *J. Phys. radium.*, 1910, **9**, 547.
3. O. STERN, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1924, **30**, 508.
4. P. BECHER, "Emulsions: Theory and Practice", p. 121, Reinhold Publishing Corp., New York, 1965.
5. D. C. HENRY, *Proc. Roy. Soc. (London)*, 1931, **106A**, 133.
6. F. BOOTH, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1951, **19**, 1331.
7. M. V. SMOLUCHOWSKI, *Bull. Acad. Sci. Cracovie.*, 1903, 182.
8. M. VAN DER WAARDEN, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1954, **9**, 215.
9. L. YA. KREMNEV and S. A. SOSKIN, *J. Gen. Chem. (U.S.S.R.)*, 1946, **16**, 2000; *Chem. Abstrs.*, 1947, **41**, 6791.
10. J. O. SIBREE, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, **26**, 26; 1931, **27**, 161.
11. L. YA. KREMNEV and S. A. SOSKIN, *Kolloid Zhur.*, 1947, **9**, 269; *Chem. Abstrs.*, 1953, **47**, 943.
12. L. YA. KREMNEV and N. I. KUIBINA, *Kolloid Zhur.*, 1951, **13**, 38.
13. N. A. FIBUROVSKII and M. F. FUTRAN, *Kolloid Zhur.*, 1947, **9**, 392; *Chem. Abstrs.*, 1949, **43**, 5256.
14. A. V. BROMBERG, *Kolloid Zhur.*, 1947, **9**, 23.
15. Ref. 4, p. 267.
16. Ref. 4, p. 401.
17. K. D. JAIN and M. K. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 991.
18. Ref. 4, p. 101.
19. R. K. NEOGY and B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **29**, 573.
20. K. D. JAIN and M. K. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 989.